

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH AT UNIVERSITY EDUCATION

Saydalieva Aziza Ergashevna

The teacher of Karshi Irrigation and Agrotechnologies Institute

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8055804>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 11th June 2023

Accepted: 18th June 2023

Online: 19th June 2023

KEY WORDS

Innovative methods, teaching methods, basic methods, Classical approach, linguistic-cultural method, communicative approach.

ABSTRACT

The article discusses about the methods of teaching English in secondary schools. Development and major changes in language learning methods are undoubtedly related to innovations in the field of individual and group psychology. Traditional and innovative methods of foreign language teaching are also analyzed.

At the end of the 20th century, there was a "revolution" in the method of teaching English in science. Previously, all priorities were given to grammar, almost mechanical acquisition of vocabulary, reading and literary translation. Now, to achieve a high social position requires a lot of hard work, perseverance and daily work. Foreign language teachers suddenly became the center of public attention: legions of experts in science, culture, business, technology and all other spheres of human activity demanded the teaching of foreign languages as a tool of production. They are not interested in the theory or history of the language - foreign languages, primarily English, are only functionally necessary for their use as a means of real communication with people from other countries in various spheres of society.

Advances and fundamental changes in language learning methods are undoubtedly associated with innovations in the field of individual and group psychology. Now there are significant changes in the minds of people and the development of a new way of thinking: the need for self-awareness and self-awareness is declared. In learning foreign languages, the psychological factor is taking the leading place. The authenticity of communication, balanced demands and claims, mutual interests, respect for the freedom of other people - this is a set of unwritten rules for establishing constructive relationships in the "teacher-student" system.

Fundamental technique

It is indeed the oldest and most traditional technique. Fundamental methodology is heavily relied upon in language universities. The translator is never sure that he knows a foreign language, he perfectly understands the unpredictability of the speech situations that arise.

Students studying according to the classical methodology not only work with different lexical layers, but also learn to look at the world through the eyes of a "native speaker" - a native speaker.

Classic approach to learning a foreign language

In this regard, the classical approach to learning a foreign language has also changed a little, but the solid principles of the "classics" of Russian language methods have been preserved. Sometimes they are actively used in schools of other methodological directions. The classical course is designed for students of different ages and often involves learning the language "from scratch". The teacher's tasks include the traditional but important aspects of pronunciation formation, the formation of a grammatical basis, and the elimination of psychological and linguistic barriers that prevent communication. "Classics" did not change the goals, but the methods are already different due to the new approach.

The classical approach is based on the understanding of language as a real and full-fledged means of communication, that is, it is necessary to systematically and harmoniously develop all language components - oral and written speech, listening, etc. in students. . The classical technique makes language partly an end in itself, but this cannot be considered a disadvantage. Such a comprehensive approach is primarily aimed at developing students' ability to understand and create speech. The methodology includes training with Uzbek teachers, but such a procedure (although not completely "fashionable") cannot be considered a disadvantage: a non-native teacher teaches a bilingual system has the ability to analyze and compare, compare constructions, convey information. better, explain grammar rules, avoid possible mistakes. The general enthusiasm for foreign specialists is a temporary phenomenon, because the Western world has highly valued the priority of bilingualism (knowledge of two languages). In today's world, the greatest value is represented by teachers who can think in a bicultural context and impart a relevant body of knowledge to students.

Linguistic sociocultural method

One of the most serious and comprehensive methods of learning a foreign language is linguistic-sociocultural, involving an appeal to such a component as the social and cultural environment. Proponents of this method firmly believe that a language loses its life when teachers and students aim to master only "lifeless" lexical and grammatical forms. Someone remarked that "personality is a product of culture." Language too. And our language mistakes confirm this most convincingly. An English learner may use the grammatically correct expression The Queen and Her relatives, but a Briton will have a hard time understanding what The Royal Family means; or, for example, the phrase "The hero is the loudspeaker of the author" was translated by the sentence "The hero is the loudspeaker of the author", and ideally it was required to use "mouthpiece". Such curiosities are quite common. Let us turn to more subtle matters: for example, if for our compatriot who has a superficial command of the language, the difference between the expressions Don't you want to go? and Would you like to go? is not very great, then for the Briton it is of principle, because he will perceive the first as not the best tone. The usual for our business communication What questions are you interested in? often translated as "What problems are you interested in?" The correct question would sound: "What issues are you interested in?" Most of the methods initially allow such "blunders", attributing them to "ignorance of the country." But at the present stage,

when interest in individual cultures and nations is constantly growing, such mistakes are already unforgivable.

The linguistic-sociocultural method takes into account the simple fact that 52% of mistakes are made under the influence of the native language, and 44% are hidden within the studied language. Previously, they monitored the correctness of speech; now, in addition to this, they strive to increase its content. The meaning of the transmitted information is important, that is, the communicative level, because in any case, the ultimate goal of communication is to be understood.

The linguistic-sociocultural method includes two aspects of communication - linguistic and intercultural. Our lexicon has been replenished with a new word bicultural - a person who is easily guided by national characteristics, history, culture, customs of two countries, civilizations, if you like, worlds. For a student of a language university, it is not so much a high level of reading, writing, and translation that is important (although this is by no means excluded), but "linguo-socio-cultural competence" - the ability to "dissect" a language under the microscope of culture.

The linguistic sociocultural method was born at the intersection of the concepts of language and culture. The authors of the method (among them S.G. Ter-Minasova occupies one of the main places) approached these definitions in a different way. The classics, in particular Ozhegov, understood language as "an instrument of communication, exchange of thoughts and mutual understanding of people in society." Dahl treated the language more simply - as "the totality of all the words of the people and their correct combination, to convey their thoughts." But animals also have language as a system of signs and a means of expressing emotions and moods. What makes speech "human"? Today, language is "not only a vocabulary, but also a person's way of expressing himself." It serves for "purposes of communication and is able to express the entire body of knowledge and ideas of a person about the world." In the West, language is understood as a "communication system", which consists of certain fragments and a set of rules used for the purpose of communication.

A very important difference between Western linguistic thinking is the understanding of language not only in connection with a certain state, but also with a certain part of the country, region, etc. With this approach, the language goes hand in hand with the culture of a part of the country, region, that is, with the ideas, customs of a certain group of people, society. Sometimes culture is understood as society itself, civilization.

We believe that the definition of the supporters of the linguo-sociocultural method does not exaggerate the strength and significance of language in the modern world. In their opinion, language is "a powerful social tool that forms the flow of people into an ethnos, forming a nation through the storage and transmission of culture, traditions, social consciousness of a given speech complex. With this approach to language, intercultural communication is, first of all," adequate mutual understanding of two interlocutors or people exchanging information belonging to different national cultures. "Then their language becomes" a sign of the belonging of its speakers to a certain society. "

However, culture often acts not only as a means of unification, identification, but also as a tool for separating people. For example, in medieval Russia, a foreigner was first called a German, that is, "dumb" who did not know the language, then a foreign guest was called a

foreigner, that is, "a stranger among their own." And finally, when the national consciousness made it possible to smooth out this opposition of "friends and foes", a foreigner appeared. If you think about the meaning of the Uzbek word foreign, then the origin of the "conflict of cultures" becomes clearer:

"Its internal form is absolutely transparent: from other countries. Native, not from other countries, culture unites people and at the same time separates them from other, foreign cultures. In other words, native culture is both a shield that protects the national identity of a people, and a blank fence that fenders off from other peoples and cultures. "

The linguistic socio-cultural method combines linguistic structures (grammar, vocabulary, etc.) with extra-linguistic factors. Then, at the junction of the worldview on a national scale and language, that is, a kind of way of thinking (let's not forget that a person belongs to the country in whose language he thinks), that rich world of language is born, about which the linguist W. von Humboldt wrote : "Through the diversity of language, the richness of the world and the diversity of what we learn in it open up for us ..." We get to know the world through thinking in a certain cultural field and use language to express our impressions, opinions, emotions, perception.

The purpose of learning a language using this method is to facilitate understanding of the interlocutor, the formation of perception at an intuitive level. Therefore, every student who has chosen such an organic and holistic approach should treat the language as a mirror that reflects the geography, climate, history of the people, their living conditions, traditions, way of life, everyday behavior, creativity.

Communicative approach

The first line in the rating of the popularity of methods is actively held by the communicative approach, which, as its name implies, is aimed at the practice of communication. This technique works great in Europe and the United States.

The communicative technique, as its name implies, is aimed precisely at the possibility of communication. Of the 4 "whales" that support any language training (reading, writing, speaking and listening), the latter two receive increased attention. You will not hear particularly complex syntactic constructions or serious vocabulary in the classroom. Oral speech of any literate person is quite different from written speech. Try to keep track of yourself throughout the day: how many long sentences have you used? Constructions in the subjunctive mood? Unfortunately, the epistolary genre is becoming a thing of the past, and if our descendants judge us only on the basis of e-mails and other "monuments" of network literature, then their opinion will hardly be flattering.

However, it would be a mistake to think that the communicative method is intended only for light small talk. Those who want to be a professional in a particular field regularly read publications on their topic in foreign publications. Possessing a large vocabulary, they can easily navigate the text, but it costs them enormous efforts to maintain a conversation with a foreign colleague on the same topic. The communicative method is designed, first of all, to remove the fear of communication. A person armed with a standard set of grammatical constructions and a vocabulary of 600-1000 words will easily find a common language in an unfamiliar country. However, there is also a downside to the coin: cliché phrases and a poor vocabulary. Add to this a lot of grammatical mistakes, and you will understand that the only

way not to be known as, say, a stupid interlocutor is to pay more attention to partners, knowledge of etiquette and a constant desire to improve. Those who study according to the communicative method are "light cavalry". They are prancing under the walls of the fortress, making swift attacks and wanting to tear down the flag, not noticing how beautiful the besieged citadel is.

So, to sum up, the British methods have a number of distinctive features. Most of them are developed based on the integration of traditional and modern teaching methods. Differentiation by age groups and a multilevel approach make it possible to develop an individual human personality, affect its worldview, value system, self-identification, and the ability to think. Simply put, the focus is on the now popular individual approach. Without exception, all British methods are aimed at developing four language skills: reading, writing, speaking and listening. At the same time, great emphasis is placed on the use of audio, video and interactive resources. Thanks to a variety of methodological techniques, among which one of the leading places is taken by language technologies, British courses contribute to the formation of the skills necessary for a person in modern business life (the ability to make a report, conduct presentations, conduct correspondence, etc.). The indisputable "pluses" of British developers are the compilation of a course based on authentic material, great attention to style, the desire to teach "situational" and "live" English through "life" examples of semi-real characters.

Some (but not all) techniques are distinguished by a good systematization of the material. Perhaps the British methods are the best option for those who want to study "real English" or pursue a narrowly specific goal of linguistic training. On the domestic methodological market there are products for every taste, and it remains only to decide on the goals, means, and most importantly - methods. Then the choice of courses and training programs will not be so difficult.

References:

1. Mirolyubov AA, History of Russian methods of teaching foreign languages. M: 2002.
2. Pavlovskaya I. Yu. Methods of teaching foreign languages (course of lectures in English): Review of modern teaching methods - 2nd ed., Isp. and add. - SPB.: Publishing house of St. Petersburg. University, 2003.
3. Bakirova H.B. Formation of lexical skills in learning foreign language terminology in a non-language university/ Emergent: journal of educational discoveries and lifelong learning (EJEDL) ISSN 2776-0995 Vol. 2, Issue 5, 2021, Indonesia.
4. Bakirova H.B. (2021) "Development of lexical competence based on content -based approach in ESP teaching, "Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal: Vol. 2021: Iss. 5, Article 19. Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/tziuj/vol2021/iss5/19>
5. Bakirova H.B. Formation of terminological competence in ESP education. Novateur publications. Journal NX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, ISSN No: 2581 - 4230 VOLUME 6, ISSUE 11, India. -2020. P 63.
6. Bakirova H.B. Teaching foreign language terminology at non-language universities. International journal of discourse on innovation. Integration and education. Volume: 01 Issue: 01. 2020 <http://summusjournals.uz/index.php/ijdiie>

7. Bakirova H.B. Terminological competence of the specialist in training vocabulary of specialty/Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN 2776-0979 Vol. 2, Issue 5, 2021, Indonesia.
8. Bakirova H. Typology of methodological and linguistic difficulties in the formation of lexical competence. ACTA NUUz. 1/5/1 2021. 44p.
9. <http://science.nuu.uz/uzmu.php>